

EFFECT OF LIGHTNING STRIKE ON THE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS – A FINITE ELEMENT STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The usage of composite materials as structural components has been increasing due to their high strength to weight ratio and corrosion resistance. They are widely used in aircraft, automobile and wind turbine industries. The response of composite materials to various types of mechanical and thermal loads is well understood. However, the response of these materials towards electric current is yet to be explored in detail. Post-lightning strike, the material would be subjected to resistive heating, which in turn leads to change in the mechanical properties. As composites are weaker in compression than tension, the current study focuses on the compressive response of the post-lightning specimen, using finite element (FE) method. A two dimensional (2D) micro-mechanical model of a carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) was modeled and coupled electrical-thermal-structural FE analysis was carried out. The post-lightning model from this analysis was subjected to compressive displacements and the strain in the components and the corresponding change in compressive strength of the material was obtained. The analysis was carried out in the commercial software COMSOL.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have replaced the metal structures fully or partially in the recent past. Studies show that the objects such as wind turbine blades, ascending and descending aircrafts in the lower altitudes (1-5 km from ground) are more likely to be affected by lightning strike [1]. Lightning is the sudden discharge of electricity between two objects of opposite polarity. It can originate from a cloud, or an object situated on the ground. Lightning strikes can cause serious structural damage if the object being struck is a poor conductor of electricity. The material that is used for the current study is carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) as this is widely used as a structural material in aircraft and wind turbine industries and are susceptible to damage due to lightning strike. Generally, CFRPs are manufactured by embedding the carbon fibers in a polymer matrix (Vinyl ester in the current study). Although the carbon fibers are good electrical conductors, the polymer matrix in which it is embedded is a poor conductor of electricity. So, the effective electrical conductivity of CFRP is generally poor. During lightning strike, the electricity takes longer time to travel through a badly conducting material. As the travel time of electric current through a material increases, it would cause localized heating as electrical energy is converted to heat energy. This phenomenon is termed as resistive heating (Joule heating/ resistive heating). As CFRP is a poor electrical conductor, the lightning strike would cause resistive heating in it. The temperature near the vicinity of the strike area would be higher and that away from the strike area would be lower. This non-uniform temperature distribution causes changes in material properties, and results in strength reduction. A lot of studies, experimental, analytical and numerical have been conducted in the recent past on understanding the lightning strike damage of composite materials.

The earliest studies on understanding the lightning strike damage on aircrafts were conducted by Fisher and Plumer in 1977 [2] and Plumer and Robb in 1982 [3]. Their studies were mostly

experimental in nature. The simulation of lightning strike inside the laboratories was achieved by various kinds of electrical waveforms since the 1970s. The waveforms suggested by Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) (Fig. 1 (a)) are widely used as an input for simulating a lightning strike in the modern laboratories. These waveforms have been used by various researchers ([4-6]) to simulate lightning strike in the laboratory environment. With the advanced computational softwares, it is possible to model lightning strike and subsequent material damage. Few of the pioneering numerical works were conducted by Ogasawara et al. [5], Abdelal and Murphy [7], Dong et al. [8]. All these studies prove that the main cause of damage was indeed the resistive heating caused in the material.

Many theoretical models have been proposed by scientists to predict the structural behavior of the composite material subjected to elevated temperatures [9]. But generally, they were developed by modeling the composites as homogeneous materials to reduce the complexities in the analysis. But, a micromechanical approach helps accurately predict the behavior of a non-homogeneous material under various load types. But, most of the existing micromechanical studies on composite materials were focusing on the influence of thermal residual stresses that are developed during curing on the material behavior. The effect of thermal residual stresses on the overall effective moduli was studied by Wu et al. [10] on metal matrix composites. A micromechanical analytical model for predicting the tensile response of composite materials has been developed by Liu et al. [11]. Fiber breakage and progressive matrix failure with thermal residual stresses were addressed in this model. But these models were mainly focusing on the effect of thermal residual stress, which is of very low magnitude as compared to the thermal stresses generated by lightning strike.

During lightning strike, the intensity of heat generated is extremely high that it would lead to the ablation of some part of the material. During a lightning strike study, such effects cannot be neglected. The current numerical study is an attempt to observe the compressive load response of the CFRP lamina using a two dimensional (2D) micromechanical model. As composites are weaker in compression than tension, the current study focuses on the compressive response of the post- lightning specimen, using finite element (FE) method. A composite material with carbon fiber embedded in vinyl epoxy matrix was used in the current study.

2 ANALYSIS METHOD

Lightning induced heat transfer should be treated as a multiphysics problem as it involves two transport phenomena. Although composite materials contain two or more constituents, it is convenient to use a homogenized model with equivalent properties for analysis, as it reduces complexities in the numerical analysis. But, in reality, the electrical and mechanical properties of the constituents (fibers and matrix in the current study) are not comparable. The homogenized model becomes irrelevant when it is necessary to differentiate between the responses of the constituents to various types of loadings. A two dimensional (2D) micromechanical model of a single lamina with matrix and embedded fibers were used in the current numerical study (Fig. 2). The main objective of the study is to analyze the compressive load response of a post-lightning specimen.

It is already mentioned in the previous section that the lightning causes resistive heating, which in turn causes change in its material properties. As a result, the response of a post-lightning material to various types of loads would be different than that of a virgin material. In the current study, the main cause of damage was identified as the heat that would be generated during the lightning strike.

This study mainly has two stages. A coupled electrical-thermal-structural analysis stage, where the temperature due to resistive heating and the thermal stresses developed during lightning strike was evaluated. It was assumed that the material would be ablated when the temperature reaches the ablation temperature. This ablation temperature is different for fiber and matrix. As the temperature increases, the modulus of elasticity of both fiber (E_f) and matrix (E_m) decrease which would lead to a reduction in strength of the material. Hence, in this study, the modulus of elasticity was given as a function of temperature. It was assumed that E_f and E_m would be reduced to 100000 GPa and 2GPa at their respective ablation temperatures. The ablation temperature of fiber and matrix were assumed to be 3000°C and 100°C respectively. In order to avoid convergence issues in the numerical model, the modulus of elasticity was defined using a smooth step function. Further, this model would be subjected to compression and the structural response was observed. It is already mentioned that the

waveform suggested by SAE (Fig. 1) will be used to simulate lightning strike. The study was conducted for four different peak currents using the waveform shown in Fig. 1(b).

Figure 1: (a) The SAE waveform for lightning strike experiments, (b) Sample waveform used in the current study [5].

2.1 The general procedure

During lightning strike, the electrical energy (Q_e) would be converted to the heat energy, and is obtained from Eq.1. The electrical energy, thus calculated is given as the source term in the heat transfer equation (Eq. 2). The temperature in the material due to the resistive heating is obtained by solving the heat transfer equation (Eq. 2). This temperature from Eq. 2 would be input as the thermal load in the structural mechanics solver to calculate thermal strain and stress (Eq. 3). This procedure repeats until the input time ends. As the temperature gets updated in each step, the material properties would also get updated. Further, the entire model would be subjected to compression and the structural response would be studied.

The electrical energy is calculated by the electric current solver by the following equation:

$$Q_e = J.E \quad (1)$$

Where, Q_e is the electric energy.

J is the current density.

E is the electric field strength.

The heat transfer equation is as follows:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) = Q_e \quad (2)$$

Where, ρ is the density of the material

C_p is the specific heat at constant pressure

T is the temperature

t is the time

k is the thermal conductivity of the material

Thermal strain and stress:

$$\mathcal{E} = \alpha \Delta T; \sigma = E(T) \mathcal{E} \quad (3)$$

Where, ϵ is the strain due to the temperature difference ΔT and σ is the corresponding stress. $E(T)$ is the temperature dependent modulus of elasticity.

The following flow chart illustrates the various steps taken by the coupled electrical-thermal-structural solver.

3 THE FINITE ELEMENT (FE) MODEL

A micromechanical model of a single lamina with dimensions 0.105 mm x 0.315 mm was modeled in COMSOL. A lamina consisting of unidirectional fibers with fiber misalignment was considered for the study. In order to create fiber imperfection, the mode shape obtained from a linear buckling analysis on a perfect model was imposed on the micro-model [12]. The amplitude of the imperfection is termed fiber misalignment. The buckled shape of the perfect model is shown in Fig. 2 (b). The amplitude of the misalignment (ϕ) was calculated by $\phi = \tan^{-1}(\frac{\Delta H}{L})$, where, ΔH is the maximum amplitude at the top of the model, and L is the length of the model.

Figure 2: (a) The perfect model, (b) The buckled shape and (c) The meshed model with fiber misalignment

An arbitrary compressive load was given to the perfect model (Fig. 2(a)) which was fixed at the bottom. The scaled buckled shape is given in Fig. 2(b). In the current study, it was decided to use $\phi = 2.25^\circ$. So, the actual ΔH required for $\phi = 2.25^\circ$ was calculated, and the existing amplitude of the buckled shape was scaled down to get the actual fiber imperfection. This new model was again meshed and coupled electrical-thermal-structural analysis was conducted as shown in the flow chart. As the temperature changes, the material properties would also change. So, temperature dependent material properties were used for the analysis. In this study, the left side of the model was exposed to the atmosphere and the current was applied on that face.

For the electrical analysis, the voltage at the top bottom and right side of the model was set to zero as there would be electrical conduction to all these sides, and electrical current was applied to the mid portion of the left side. The current intensity is calculated by $R(t) = 6.86 \times 10^{-4} (I_{\text{peak}})^{(1/3)}$, where R is the lightning channel radius, t is the time, I is the peak current [13]. For the thermal analysis, convective heat transfer was assumed and a heat transfer coefficient of $10 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$ was given on the left side. The initial temperature was assumed as 293.15 K . For structural analysis, the bottom of the model was fixed. As the coupled electrical-thermal analysis would cause non-uniform temperature distribution, which in turn would cause change in material properties throughout the model. In other words, the heat produced would affect its stiffness as the modulus of elasticity is also a function of temperature. Further, this damaged model was input into the structural mechanics solver for the compression analysis. Newton-Raphson method was used in the compression analysis for solving the equations. The material properties used are given in Table 1.

Property	Fiber	Matrix
Electrical conductivity (S/m)	22174 (at 27°C) – 120000 (at 3000°C)	1.08×10^{-13} (at 100°C) – 4.8×10^{-13} (at 150°C)
Thermal conductivity (W/m/K)	6.7	0.0625
Specific heat at constant pressure (J/kg/K)	620 (at 27°C) – 200 (at 3000°C)	620 (at 27°C) – 200 (at 3000°C)
Density (kg/m ³)	1850	1160
Coefficient of thermal expansion(/K)	-1.4×10^{-6} (Longitudinal) & 3.8×10^{-6} (Transverse)	16×10^{-6}
Young's modulus (GPa)	276 (at 27°C) – 100000 (at 3000°C)	3.585×10^9 (at 27°C) – 2×10^9 (at 300°C)
Poisson's ratio	0.3	0.36

Table 1: The material properties used in the current study [12], [14], [15].

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The load-displacement curve of a composite material that has undergone damage would have two parts. An linear initial part, indicating that the load increases linearly with displacement and a comparatively horizontal part with a very small slope indicating that the material is no more capable of taking the load. In this region, even if there is an increment in strain, the stresses will not increase much as the material has already failed.

In the current study, the analysis did not proceed beyond $1 \mu\text{m}$ displacement as the solver was unable to capture the material response due to numerical instability. The load-displacement curve was linear till $1 \mu\text{m}$ displacement. The maximum strains in the matrix and the fiber were observed to know if they have exceeded the corresponding limits. The maximum compressive strain of vinyl ester reported by Yerramalli et al. was about 0.1 [12]. The maximum tensile strain of carbon fibers was reported as 0.016 [16].

The table shows that the strain in both fiber and matrix increases with increase in current intensity. These maximum values were observed in the vicinity of the strike area. It can be observed that the maximum strains in both fiber and matrix up to $1 \mu\text{m}$ overall displacement are below the corresponding maximum limits. However, the fiber tensile strain at 80 kA strike is about 93 % of the failure strain

(0.016). The corresponding overall strength was found to be 292 MPa. The strength of the pristine model with a fiber misalignment of 2.25° was around 560 MPa, which is close to the value (550 MPa) reported by Yerramalli et al. [12]. So, an 80 kA strike reduced the overall strength of the model by approximately 48 %.

Current (kA)	Max. fiber tensile strain	Max. matrix tensile strain	Max. matrix compressive strain
10	0.00145	0.00175	-0.00265
20	0.00145	0.00175	-0.0027
40	0.0019	0.00175	-0.00285
80	0.015	0.0017	-0.0031

Table 2: The fiber and matrix strain up to $1\mu\text{m}$ displacement.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The current study shows that the fiber strain increases with increase in the magnitude of the current. However, the complete response of the post-lightning model under compression was not captured with the existing numerical algorithm. In this model only geometrical nonlinearity is considered. In addition to that, the matrix plasticity also have to be taken into consideration to obtain a more accurate response.

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